

EBFMC25-OP-76 · Evaluation of Health Workers' Knowledge Levels and Attitudes About HPV Infection and HPV Vaccine

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15824310>

Oral Presentation #76 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress.

AUTHORS

Gadime Yanmaz
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0722-5053>

Ersan Gursoy
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5020-412X>

AFFILIATIONS

Erzincan Provincial Health Directorate
Erzincan, Turkey

Erzincan Binali Yildirim University
Faculty of Medicine
Erzincan, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Human papillomavirus (HPV) is the leading cause of cervical cancer, one of the most common cancers in women (Wakeham & Kavanagh, 2014). HPV vaccination is a highly effective preventive tool, but its use depends on the knowledge and attitudes of healthcare professionals. This study aims to identify gaps and improve vaccination efforts by assessing the awareness and perspectives of healthcare professionals in Erzincan about HPV and its vaccine.

Materials and Methods: Healthcare workers working in Erzincan province were asked to fill out a 19-question survey created by scanning the literature on HPV infection and vaccination, including sociodemographic data, via Google Surveys.

Results: This study evaluated 110 healthcare workers in Erzincan province and provided important information about HPV knowledge and prevention practices. 70% of the participants were female, 67.2% were married and 61.8% were physicians. It was determined that 100% of the participants had not had a sexually transmitted disease before and 80.9% had no warts on their bodies before. The data showed that 64.5% had sufficient knowledge about HPV infections and 90% saw cervical cancer as preventable, while there was a significant deficiency in disease prevention behaviors.

Especially despite the fact that the vaccine is considered effective (73.6%), HPV vaccination rates are significantly low at only 7.3%. Cervical cancer screening rates are similarly inadequate and 75.3% of female healthcare workers reported that they had never had a Pap smear test. 62.7% of the participants reported that they would vaccinate their children if the HPV vaccine was added to Türkiye's national immunization schedule and was free of charge. 50.9% of the participants thought that the HPV vaccine had very few side effects, yet vaccine hesitancy remained widespread. 70% of the participants rejected the idea that the vaccine was merely a profit-making scheme for pharmaceutical companies.

Conclusion: Despite healthcare workers' awareness of HPV risks, low vaccination and screening rates in Erzincan underscore the need for free national HPV vaccine programs and targeted education to bridge knowledge-practice gaps.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

HPV, HPV vaccine, cervical cancer, healthcare worker

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

Wakeham, K., & Kavanagh, K. (2014). The burden of HPV-associated anogenital cancers. *Current oncology reports, 16*, 1-11.

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Gadime Yanmaz

Erzincan Provincial Health Directorate

Erzincan, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0722-5053>

gdimeisk@hotmail.com